

Raising a green baby in Bangladesh: Perspective Analysis

Md. Mizanur Rahman

Information and Communication Technology Division, Bangladesh

E-mail: rahmanboku@gmail.com

Abstract

The overall objective of the study is to develop a model to raise a child in an eco-friendly environment in a country like Bangladesh. Empirical data was used in this study. Based on the respondents' perceptions a model was developed for a green baby's lifestyle at the low cost or no cost. Breastfeeding is highly recommended by the respondents for boosting the immunity system against diseases and reducing health care and feeding costs. A Green mom is a prerequisite for a green baby. Cloth diapers are more comfortable and healthier than disposable diapers. Handing down baby clothes is a huge cost saving. Baby food, bed, and toys should be organic. Making a child a part of the recycling process and nature conservation is warranted to raise a green child.

Keywords: Green baby, breastfeeding, green mom, organic food, handing down, recycling process, nature conservation

Introduction

A baby living in an eco-friendly, healthier, safer and happier place is called a green baby. A greener life dedicated to sustainability is the prime condition of becoming a green baby. Green Baby defines green, eco-friendly, congenial, frugal, sustainable, simple, healthy and happy life, and sustainable communities for children so that they can live the lives they want to live (Lorenzen, 2012). Going green is to benefit the broader environment: fight climate change, reduce air pollution and curtail the harm that inflicts on the planet and its many species. It is important for the health and well-being of humanity.

Go green and green baby means finding a balance between the life they lead, the impact that life and their choices have on the planet, and being mindful enough to help maintain ecological balance to preserve the planet, its ecosystems, and its natural resources. A baby needs to live more harmoniously with nature and safeguard the future of the human species and recognize that they are a part of nature, not separate from it. Eco-friendly is a term typically used to describe a product and how it's made. For a product to be genuinely eco-friendly it has to take both earth and human health into account. The resources used to make the item need to come from sustainable resources. For clothing that means the materials used are grown without the use of harmful pesticides and herbicides. Organic wool, hemp, and natural cotton are three examples.

In contrast, poverty, environmental degradation, food adulteration and overpopulation are the main challenges in Bangladesh (Rahman, 2021, a, b). Acute respiratory infection (ARI) is a major cause of childhood mortality and morbidity in Bangladesh. Malnutrition, illiteracy, and family socioeconomic status were associated with this infection (Azad, 2008). Children with Disabilities face multifaceted challenges to avail of fundamental civil rights and essential services such as education, healthcare and treatment (Akter and Rahman, 2018). The intake of some metals through foods was higher than the recommended values in Bangladesh, which were associated with carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health risks (Islam *et al.* 2015). Considering these challenges, the study attempted to develop a model to raise a child in an eco-friendly environment.

Methodology

Empirical data was used for this study. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders like child specialists, physicians, environmentalists and parents. A total number of 10 key respondents were interviewed to develop a model for raising an eco-friendly baby. Content analysis was done categorically.

How to raise a green baby?

Breastfeeding

Breastfeeding is highly recommended for the green baby. When the mother of the child is eating well, then the baby is eating well, there's no more difficulty with that "formula." Mother's breast milk is the healthiest form of milk for human babies. But there are some exceptions, such as when the mother is taking certain drugs or is infected with dangerous contagious diseases. It accelerates physical and mental growth; builds up immunity against diseases; and reduces health care and feeding costs.

Green mom

At first, a mom goes green for growing a green baby. The mother should avoid amalgam fillings in any dental work. Hair dyes are harmful to the baby. She should eat organic foods. The smoker mom should quit smoking to avoid a smoky environment. Cigarette smoke is dangerous to babies. Drugs and alcohols are also harmful to the baby. The mom should reduce her exposure to aluminium by not using aluminium pots or cookware, deodorant or antiperspirant containing aluminium.

Saying "no" to disposable diapers

Disposable diapers are much more harmful to the environment and the baby than cloth diapers. It is also a possible danger of contaminating groundwater. It may take several hundred years for the decomposition of disposables to take place, with some of the plastic material never decomposing. It is not possible to keep a baby's skin dry, healthy and free from diaper rash with disposable diapers. Prolonged wetness, lack of air circulation, and chemical and dye cause irritations to the baby. Sodium polyacrylate (the super absorbent gel), and dioxin (a by-product of bleaching paper)

are used to prepare the disposable diapers. Sodium polyacrylate has been linked in the past to toxic shock syndrome, allergic reactions and is very harmful and potentially lethal to pets. Dioxin is known to cause damage to the central nervous system, kidneys, and liver.

Saying “yes” to “hand me downs”

Handing down baby clothes is a very old and true practice. It is a huge cost savings. Hand-me-down baby clothes, or "used" baby clothing need not be a dirty word. Without a wallet shrinking the wardrobe grows very quickly. By accepting "previously enjoyed" clothing again, a parent can serve as the pebble in the pond. "Hand me Downs" is a basic principle of sustainable development.

Using organic products in the home

"Simple green" is good for the environment since pristine times. For an organic lifestyle for a baby, the parent will love organic resources for switching to a greener way of life. The organic cosmetics and natural skincare will be free from parabens, SLS, synthetic fragrances and mineral oil or propylene glycol.

Organic baby foods

Before weaning, it is essential to know that there are no chemicals like fertilizer or pesticide residues in the food. As your baby grows and you begin to wean, go ahead and introduce organic baby goods. Organic baby food will be prepared from naturally good ingredients grown without chemical pesticides, nitrates, growth hormones or other unwanted extras and the meals will be produced without artificial additives or processing chemicals. For growing infants or toddlers, the foods will be free from salt, preservatives, gluten, dairy, additives, sugars and/or fillers.

Organic toys

Organic toys are made from stuffed animals, wood and toxic-free pure fabrics (cotton). Organic toys help a child's imagination flourish. The fabrics will be colourful but not dyed. This is achieved simply by using fibres from naturally occurring brown, green or white varieties of the cotton plant, thereby producing coloured fabric without using any dyes. Low-impact “reactive”, safe and environmentally-friendly dyes may be used. Harmful chemicals like formaldehyde cannot be used during the finishing process to give a material a soft or shiny quality.

Organic baby bedding

Baby bedding should be eco-friendly. Organic crib mattresses on soft bamboo sheets can bring a bundle of joy for the little angels. Organic pads and blankets create a green environment daily for the green baby. To protect your organic crib mattress, an organic wool puddle pad can be used directly over the crib mattress. Wool is highly absorbent and provides the best natural protection without resorting to a plastic barrier.

Figure 1: A green baby (Nuhad Nudrat) is on an organic bed made of animal hair and skin

Organic sippy cup

Non-leaching, safe sippy cups made the stainless-steel alternative to plastic can be used for the green baby. They are odour free and have no metal-like taste. Plastic/polycarbonate bottles leach bisphenol-A (BPA), a chemical that mimics the hormone estrogen and can cause chromosomal abnormalities.

Green painting

Any renovation of the home should be avoided. Lead-containing paint is very harmful to the baby. For the decoration of the new nursery plant-based paints with low fumes can be used. Solvents and fume-emitting adhesives are strictly prohibited in the baby nursery.

Making a child a part of the recycling process

As the child begins to walk and becomes more mobile, we should train them to place "trash" in its appropriate place. By teaching the first word "recycle," we can be proud green parents.

Setting the green examples: The parents should tell and cite green examples like a mountain lion having an organic diet will win over an alligator in a fight. Let our kiddos see we buy organic, cook organic, recycle, reduce, reuse and enjoy the fruits of being eco-friendly by enjoying the great outdoors.

Nature conservation

Unless and until we all are involved in nature conservation, beautiful destinations may not be here for our green child to enjoy.

References

Akter A and Rahman M (2018) Women with disabilities in Bangladesh: accessibility in the build environment. *Proshikhyan, J Train Dev* 26(2):1–12.

Azad, K. M. A. K. (2008). Risk Factors for Acute Respiratory Infections (ARI) Among Under-five Children in Bangladesh. *Journal of Scientific Research*, 1(1), 72–81. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jsr.v1i1.1055>

Lorenzen, J.A. (2012), Going Green: The Process of Lifestyle Change. *Sociological Forum*, 27: 94-116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1573-7861.2011.01303.x>

Md. Saiful Islam, Md. Kawser Ahmed, Md. Habibullah-Al-Mamun, Mohammad Raknuzzaman (2015). The concentration, source and potential human health risk of heavy metals in the commonly consumed foods in Bangladesh, *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, Volume 122: 462-469, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2015.09.022>.

Rahman, M. M. (2021a). Achieving Sustainable Development Goals of Agenda 2030 in Bangladesh: the crossroad of the governance and performance. *Public Administration and Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PAP-12-2020-0056>.

Rahman, M. M. (2021). Can ordinary people seek environmental justice in Bangladesh? Analyzing through the lens of legal, policy, and institutional framework. *Bangladesh Journal of Public Administration*, 29(2), 15–34. <https://doi.org/10.36609/bjpa.v29i2.226>.

Rahman, MM (2021b) Consumers' Perceptions of Organic Foods in Bangladesh: Challenges and Opportunities (January 17, 2021). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3767725>.